

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF TOLERANT THINKING OF FUTURE SOCIAL WORK SPECIALISTS.

Ergashev Ikhtiyor Bakhtiyor ugli

Teacher of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15472417>

Annotation: This article is devoted to the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation and development of tolerant thinking of future social work specialists. The article presents the concept of tolerance, its role in social work, the components of tolerant thinking, as well as the pedagogical and methodological foundations of the formation of this thinking. The integration of tolerance into the education system, the necessary courses and methods in the curricula, various methods of developing tolerance in practice are discussed in detail. The article also emphasizes the importance of tolerant thinking in social work and its impact on professional success. The formation of tolerance in social work requires a systematic and continuous approach, in which methodologies and practices must be consistent with each other.

Keywords: tolerance, social work, thinking, pedagogical foundations, methodology, practice, tolerance, empathy, multiculturalism, social services, education system, professional training, humanistic approach.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola bo'lajak ijtimoiy ish mutaxassislarining tolerantlik tafakkurini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodik asoslariga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada tolerantlik tushunchasi, uning ijtimoiy ishda o'rni, tolerantlik tafakkurining tarkibiy qismlari, shuningdek, bu tafakkurni shakllantirishning pedagogik va metodik asoslari keltirilgan. Tolerantlikning ta'lim tizimiga integratsiyasi, o'quv dasturlarida kerakli kurslar va metodlar, amaliyotda tolerantlikni rivojlantirishning turli usullari batafsil yoritilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada tolerantlik tafakkurining ijtimoiy ishdagi ahamiyati va uning kasbiy muvaffaqiyatga ta'siri ta'kidlangan. Ijtimoiy ishda tolerantlikni shakllantirish tizimli va uzluksiz yondashuvni talab qiladi, bunda metodika va amaliyotlar bir-biriga mos kelishi lozim.

Kalit so'zlar: tolerantlik, ijtimoiy ish, tafakkur, pedagogik asoslar, metodika, amaliyot, bag'rikenglik, empatiya, multikulturalizm, ijtimoiy xizmatlar, ta'lim tizimi, kasbiy tayyorgarlik, gumanistik yondashuv.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена теоретико-методологическим основам формирования и развития толерантного мышления будущих специалистов социальной работы. В статье представлено понятие толерантности, ее роль в социальной работе, компоненты толерантного

мировоззрения, а также педагогические и методические основы формирования этого мировоззрения. Подробно рассматриваются вопросы интеграции толерантности в систему образования, необходимые курсы и методики в учебных программах, а также различные методы развития толерантности на практике. В статье также подчеркивается важность толерантного мышления в социальной работе и его влияние на профессиональный успех. Формирование толерантности в социальной работе требует системного и непрерывного подхода, при котором методологии и практики должны соответствовать друг другу.

Ключевые слова: толерантность, социальная работа, мышление, педагогические основы, методология, практика, толерантность, эмпатия, мультикультурализм, социальные услуги, система образования, профессиональная подготовка, гуманистический подход.

In modern society, cooperation, tolerance, mutual respect and compromise are among the important values among people. Especially in countries with multinational, multi-faith and diverse cultures, these values are necessary to ensure social stability in society. From this perspective, the mindset of tolerance should be formed as one of the main competencies in the professional training of social workers.

In particular, today, the establishment of Social Work Departments in higher educational institutions in order to improve the social life of society is being manifested as a form of state social policy aimed directly at improving the social lifestyle of people. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev's Decree No. PF-82 dated June 1, 2023 "On comprehensive measures to provide high-quality social services and assistance to the population and establish an effective control system for them"[1], Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-319 dated September 28, 2023 "On measures to further improve the system of providing social services and assistance to the population"[2], Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 654 dated October 21, 2021 "On measures to further improve the system of social protection of the population" and other regulatory and legal documents indicate the relevance of this area.[3]

The field of social work is aimed at working directly with people, understanding their problems and helping them, and professionals in this profession must have the skills to communicate effectively with people of different categories. Tolerance is not only tolerance, but also understanding, respecting and accepting the worldview, lifestyle and values of others.[4]

Theoretical foundations of the concept of tolerance.

1. Tolerance (lat. tolerantia - endurance, tolerance) is an approach based on understanding and respect towards people with different opinions, beliefs, cultures and lifestyles. This concept is closely related to human rights, democracy, civil society and sustainable development.

2. A tolerant mindset is a person's ability to understand others, recognize their uniqueness, accept the existence of opposing views and evaluate them correctly. This mindset should be combined with a conscious approach and ethical position.

3. The role of tolerance in social work. A social worker deals with the following problems:

- working with people with disabilities;
- establishing contact with the elderly and lonely;
- working with migrants or national minorities;
- dealing with family and children's problems.[5]

In each case, a social worker must be respectful and tolerant towards people with different worldviews.

Components of tolerant thinking.

Tolerant thinking is multifaceted and consists of the following components:

1. Cognitive component - Knowledge about others: awareness of different cultures, religions, beliefs and traditions.

2. Emotional component - Empathy, sympathy and the ability to understand the situation of other people.

3. Volitional component - Patience in difficult situations, a positive approach and the desire to resolve the situation peacefully.

4. Moral (ethical) component - The ideas of justice, respect for human rights, equality and humanity.

Pedagogical foundations of the formation of tolerant thinking.

1. Approach in the education system

The following are important in the training of future social workers:

- Humanistic approach - a student-centered approach.
- Dialogic education - open communication, appreciation of diversity of opinions.
- Interactive methods - trainings, role-playing games, debates.

2. Integrating tolerance into the curriculum

To develop tolerance competence, the following courses can be included in the curriculum:

- “Fundamentals of social culture”
- “Multiculturalism and intercultural dialogue”
- “Social ethical norms”. [6]

Methods for developing tolerant thinking.

1. Trainings and psychological exercises

Understanding personal problems, putting oneself in the place of others, increasing stress resistance.

2. Case study (analysis of situations)

Study of problem situations based on real-life examples and finding solutions based on tolerance.

3. Role-playing games and dramas

Lively reflection of compromise, balance and dialogue between different groups.

4. Creative tasks and projects

Creating videos, articles, social campaigns on the topic of tolerance.

Practice of forming tolerance in social work.

The practice of forming a tolerant mindset in social work can be implemented in the following forms:

1. Social services and practices: Social work professionals need to demonstrate tolerance in their practice, communicate sincerely and openly with others when solving various problems.

2. Individual approach to providing social services: An individual approach to each person, understanding their needs and knowing how best to meet these needs is important in social work. Tolerance acts as an important tool in this case.

3. Social projects and volunteering: Students learn to apply tolerance in practice through active participation in social services or social projects. This experience helps them develop skills in communicating with different social groups.[7]

Conclusion. The formation of a tolerant mindset in future social workers is an important foundation for their professional success, an active role in ensuring stability and harmony in society. The development of tolerance requires a systematic, comprehensive and continuous approach. In this regard, the education system, methodology, and practice must be harmonious. Only then will a positive environment be created among all segments of society through the field of social work.

References:

1. <https://lex.uz/docs/-6480342>

2. <https://lex.uz/docs/-6624639>
3. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5688101>
4. Latipova N., G'aniyeva M. Ijtimoiy ish etikasi. Darslik. –T. : “Fan va texnologiya”, 2015, -B. 100.
5. Qarshiyeva G. Ma'naviy yetuklik//Jamiyat va boshqaruv, 2006.-B-15
6. Usmonova E.Z. O'quvchilarda mustaqil tafakkurni qanday shakllantirish mumkin? – T.: TDPU, 2000. – b.15
7. Shodmonova Sh. Oliy o'quv yurti talabalarida mustaqillik tafakkurini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish (Kasb ta'limi yo'nalishi misolida): Ped. fan. dok. ...diss. – T.: TDPU, 2010. – b. 43

